

young, actively growing cultures of virulent (V_1, V_2) and avirulent (AV_1, AV_2) types, each consisting of about 10^9 cells/ml, were mixed in different proportions (see figure) and inoculated separately by pin-prick (PP) and leaf-tip-cut (TC) techniques in flag leaves of the host. Disease intensity (DI) — average leaf lesion length (cm) of 3 replications — was recorded 15 d after inoculation. Disease increase or reduction over check was assessed as average DI of PP and TC inoculations, expressed in percentage.

The disease-producing ability of V cultures was noticeably reduced when the AV cultures were mixed. Qualitative and quantitative disease suppression was detected. Necrosis induced by the $V + AV$ inoculum developed slowly and was characteristically discontinuous and less intensive than in the checks. Although lesion length reduction (DI) occurred even in leaves inoculated with less than 50% of the AV culture, it was significant where inoculum had 50% or more of AV culture. Inoculation with $V_1 + V_2$ combinations, however, did not show significant increase or decrease of

Percentage of increase or reduction in disease intensity over checks (inoculated with single virulent culture) at varying concentrations of virulent (V_1, V_2) plus avirulent (AV_1, AV_2) and V_1 plus V_2 cultures in inoculum.

infection over checks.

The fact that the AV forms of *X. c. pv. oryzae* interfere with the disease-producing ability of the V population of

the pathogen suggests that occurrence of AV forms is important in the epidemiology of the disease. □

Fungicidal control of rice sheath blight (ShB)

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ShB caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn (*Thanatephorus cucumeris*) is a serious disease in the wet rice-growing areas of Sri Lanka. No suitable chemicals for its control have been recommended. Since a variety resistant to ShB has yet to be found, the effectiveness of some fungicides was tested *in vitro* and *in vivo*.

Ten concentrations, 10-100 ppm, were tested against *R. solani* in PDA medium, using the filter paper disc technique. The medium in the plates was divided into four equal parts and filter paper discs dipped in fungicide solutions were placed in each quarter. A single sclerotium of *R. solani* was placed in the center of the plate. The inhibition zone

Effectiveness of fungicides on rice ShB disease incidence and grain yield. ^a Bombuwela, Sri Lanka.

Fungicide	Application time after inoculation	Disease incidence		Grain yield (t/ha)		
		1984/85 maha	1985 yala	1984/85 maha	1985 yala	1985 yala
50% benomyl	24 h	3.88 a	3.22 a	3.2	3.6	3.6
	2 wk	3.12 ab	2.55 bc	3.5	3.6	3.6
Triphenyltin hydroxide	24 h	2.50 b	2.29 c	3.6	3.5	3.5
	2 wk	3.26 ab	2.80 ab	3.6	3.6	3.6
25% pencycuron	24 h	2.38 b	2.30 c	3.6	3.6	3.6
	2 wk	2.48 b	2.52 bc	3.6	3.4	3.4
Control (no fungicide)	—	3.63 a	2.85 ab	3.1	3.2	3.2
	CV (%)	18.8	9	11.5	11.7	11.7

^a Av of 3 replications. In a column, values followed by the same letter are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT.

around each disc for each concentration was measured as the fungus grew.

Benomyl, triphenyltin hydroxide, and pencycuron were used for field tests for two seasons in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Plot size was 6 × 3 m. Rice variety BW288-1-3 was broadcast. Recommended

fertilizers were applied. Standard plant protection measures were taken.

The inoculum, 7-d-old *R. solani* cultured on rice grain, was spread evenly on the water surface at panicle initiation. Fungicides were sprayed 24 h and 2 wk after inoculation at 0.5 kg ai/ha for benomyl and triphenyltin hydroxide,

and 0.25 kg ai/ha for penycyuron.

Disease incidence was assessed at harvest as follows:

$$\text{Disease incidence} = \frac{1(H) + 2(L) + 3(M) - 4(S_1) + 5(S_2)}{\text{Total no. of tillers}}$$

H = healthy tillers, L = lightly infected

tillers, M = moderately infected tillers, S₁ = severely infected tillers, and S₂ = very severely infected tillers (flag leaf dried and killed).

Of fungicides tested in PDA medium, inhibitory zones were shown only with triphenyltin hydroxide at 10 ppm and

penycyuron at 30 ppm.

Disease incidence and yield in two seasons are given in the table. In both seasons, the lowest disease incidence was with penycyuron applied 24 h after inoculation. □

Damage by rice root-knot nematode

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Healthy seedlings of rice variety PTB10 were transplanted in 10-cm-diameter earthen pots containing sterilized soil (500 g/pot). At 6 d after planting, 0, 1, 4, and 16 *Meloidogyne graminicola* egg masses/plant were introduced in the root zone. The treatments were in 8 replications in a randomized block design. Symptoms of infestation on foliage and external symptoms and gall formation on the root system were recorded.

Disease caused by the root-knot nematode affected the entire rice plant, producing damage symptoms on foliage and roots.

On the foliage, tip drying was observed at all levels of inoculum. Leaf bronzing developed from the tip downward and from the margin toward the midrib of the leaf blade. Plants were chlorotic. There was considerable distortion in leaf emergence and growth. The leaves were crinkled (Fig. 1). New tillers had reduced height. Severely

1. Symptoms on plants showing crinkled appearance of leaves.

infected plants flowered and matured early. Emerging panicles were crinkled, grain setting was poor, and chaffiness was observed in the panicles.

Characteristic knots appeared in a string on the fibrous roots (Fig. 2). Roots showed profuse development of small, slender, lateral roots, resulting in a hairy root system.

Galls were beaded, club- or spindle-shaped. In cases of heavy infection, they coalesced and formed peculiar shapes. The minimum-size galls, which appeared 4 d after inoculation, were 300-550 μm long and 150-450 μm wide. Each gall

2. a) Root system of an infected plant. b) Different shapes of galls.

was as big as 13 mm long and 2.29 mm wide after egg production. □

Detection of seedborne rice fungi by blotter method

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Seed samples of Ratna, Jaya, IR24, Pusa 2-21, Phouren, and Moirangphou that had been collected 2-3 mo after harvest were kept in polythene bags in desiccators. Glass petri dishes and semitransparent plastic petri dishes were

used. Twenty-five seeds/petri dish were plated on three 11-cm diameter circles blotter paper moistened with water. Plates were incubated 6 d in B.O.D. incubators fitted with daylight tubes. Intact growths of fungal pathogens were examined with a stereoscopic microscope. Four hundred seeds/variety were tested under the following conditions:

Temperature. 17°C, 22 °C, 27°C, and 32°C with 12 h light. Temperature had a significant effect on percentage

infection of most fungi (Table 1). Higher infection percentages of *Pyricularia oryzae*, and *Nigrospora* spp. at 22°C were detected, higher infection percentages of *Drechslera oryzae*, *Trichoconis padwickii*, and *Curvularia* spp., at 27°C.

Light. Maximum infection percentages of most fungi were detected at 12 h/d exposure to light (Table 2).

Substrate moisture. Eight to 10 ml water were optimum to detect maximum infection percentages of most